

URBAN CHALLENGES CARDS

Here are the printable urban challenges cards for Step 2 of the Urban Mapping Workshop.

The card templates are provided in every color for each area.

Print as many as you need for each area, cut them up and and start mapping your local context!

Add the name of the identified urban challenge here
Notes...

